

YIELD OF SOYBEAN IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE NORTHERN FOREST-STEPPE OF UKRAINE DEPENDS ON MINERAL FERTILIZERS AND SEED INOCULATIONS

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ABSTRACT

For production in the conditions of the northern Forest-Steppe, it is recommended to grow the Zolotista soybean variety with the use of mineral fertilizers at the rate of $N_{40}P_{45}K_{60}$ and seed treatment with the inoculant Nitrofix - C at the rate of 1,6 kg per 1 ton of seeds.

Keywords: variety, soybean, mineral fertilizers, inoculant, morphological indicators of plants, productivity.

Formulation of the problem.

Soy is a popular crop in the field of agriculture, it provides good yields, it is grown on different types of soil, except for sandy ones. The value of soybeans lies in the content of protein and oil. This culture is used in food production - flour, oil, soy milk soy sauce. Another uniqueness of soy is that it is considered universal. Various surrogates can be made from it, such as meat, milk, chocolate etc [1, 2].

In order to increase crop productivity, it is necessary to correctly and logically make a crop rotation of alternating crops and a fertilization system, which changes the quality and content of protein and oil in the seeds of the crop.

The growth and development of plants also depends on the water-heat balance of air and soil, variety, hybrid, sowing time, tillage, phytosanitary state of crops [3].

Analysis of recent research and publications.

An important point in the cultivation of soybeans is the appropriate depth of fertilizer application, because it is the nutrients contained in the fertilizer that are easily subject to water and wind erosion.

Fertilizer rates for soybeans are calculated according to the soil and climatic conditions of the growing zone. The standard amount of fertilizers depends on the content of nutrients in the fertilizer, the mobile forms of nutrients in the soil and the planned yield [1, 5].

Regarding the fertilization of crops in crop rotation, soybean responds well to the introduction of organic fertilizers under the predecessor. Since the after-effect of organic fertilizers (manure, compost) has a duration of 3-4 years, crops are less weedy, since manure contains a large number of weed seeds [3].

Leguminous crops, including soybeans, also need bacterial fertilizers-inoculants, which are used to treat seeds directly on the day of sowing [2]. Soybean is considered a fastidious crop and therefore requires careful crop care and certain capital investments [4].

The purpose and tasks of the research.

The purpose of this work was to investigate the influence of the recommended rates of mineral fertilizers in combination with the inoculant Nitrofix - C on the growth and development of plants and the yield of soybeans of the Zolotista variety.

Research methods.

General scientific and special research methods: field (selection of soil and plant samples); laboratory (determination of the main agroecological parameters of the soil and the dynamics of plant growth and development).

Research was conducted during 2020-2021 at the "Vertokiyvka" farm of the Zhytomyr district of the Zhytomyr region. The territory of the farm belongs to the temperate soil and climate zone.

The soil is medium-loamy with a lumpy structure, the density is 1,3-1,5 g/cm³. The arable layer has the following indicators: humus content – 2,9 – 4,2 %, alkaline hydrolyzed nitrogen - 66-80 mg/kg, mobile phosphorus according to Chirkov - 140-250 mg/kg of soil, exchangeable potassium - 80-99 mg/kg soil, soil acidity – 5,5 – 6,9.

When growing soybeans, generally accepted agricultural techniques for the region of the Northern Forest Steppe were used. The seed sowing rate is 650-700 thousand

pcs. /ha.

Options for soybean fertilization:

1. Control - $N_{40}P_{45}K_{60}$
2. $N_{40}P_{45}K_{60}$ + Nitrofix - C (inoculant) - 1.6 kg per 1 ton of seeds.

Mid-early soybean variety Zolotista was used in the research. Suitable for cultivation in all climatic zones (Forest-Steppe, Polissia, Steppe). Vegetation period - 105-120 days. The main feature of the variety is the number of beans on the plant and the number of seeds in the beans. Resistant to drought, lodging and shedding of seeds.

From germination to flowering - 30-35 days. Requires active temperatures at the level of 2230° C. The height of the plant is 80-110 centimeters, 10-15 nodes

are formed on the stem. The weight of 1000 seeds is 150-165 grams. The protein content varies between 39,3-41,0 %, and the oil content - 20-22 %.

Nitrofix - C inoculant was used for seed treatment. Seed inoculation was carried out by evenly applying the drug to soybean seeds with full seed coverage.

Research results.

The main technological factors affecting the growth and development of soybean plants include mineral nutrition of plants and seed inoculation (table 1).

Table 1

Morphological indicators of plants of the Zolotista soybean variety depending on fertilizer, average for 2020-2021

Fertilization	Plant height, cm	Stem diameter, cm	Weight of plants, g
Control - N ₄₀ P ₄₅ K ₆₀	83,7	1,2	1025
N ₄₀ P ₄₅ K ₆₀ + Nitrofix - C	87,5	1,4	1129

The results of the research showed that the application of N₄₀P₄₅K₆₀ + Nitrofix - C (inoculant) contributed to the improvement of the morphological indicators of soybean plants, and the height of the plants increased by 3,8 cm, the diameter of the stem by 0,2 cm, and the weight of the plants by 104 grams.

Also, the use of mineral fertilizers in combination with the inoculant improved the characteristics of the indicators of soybeans (table 2).

At the same time, the number of seeds (1 pc.), the uniformity of seeds (0,2 %), the weight of 1000 pcs. increased soybean seeds (7 g).

Table 2

Characteristics of indicators of soybeans of the Zolotista variety, average for 2020-2021

Fertilization	Number of seeds, pcs.	Seed uniformity, %	Weight 1000 pcs. soybean seeds, g
Control - N ₄₀ P ₄₅ K ₆₀	2	94	153
N ₄₀ P ₄₅ K ₆₀ + Nitrofix - C	3	96	160

The use of mineral fertilizers and inoculant had a positive effect on improving the morphological characteristics of plants and soybeans, which, in turn, increased the yield of soybean seeds (table 3).

Table 3

The yield of the Zolotysta soybean seeds, depending on the fertilizer average for 2020-2021

Fertilization	Productivity, t/ha	Increase in yield	
		t/ha	%
Control - N ₄₀ P ₄₅ K ₆₀	2,3	-	-
N ₄₀ P ₄₅ K ₆₀ + Nitrofix - C	2,6	0,3	112
NIR ₀₅ , t/ha	0,2		

If in the control for the application of only mineral fertilizers, the yield was obtained at the level of 2,3 t/ha, then with the additional application of inoculant to mineral fertilizers, the yield increased to 2,6 t/ha, or by 0,3 t/ha. Such an increase in yield is reliable at the NIR₀₅ level of 0,2 t/ha.

Conclusion.

When growing soybean seeds of the Zolotista variety, the application of mineral fertilizers at the rate of N₄₀P₄₅K₆₀ in combination with the inoculant Nitrofix - C 1,6 kg per 1 ton of seeds in the soil-climatic zone of the northern Forest-Steppe is sufficient to significantly improve the morphological indicators of plants and obtain a seed yield at the level of 2,6 t/ha.

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